

CONCEPT, FUNCTIONS AND STRUCTURE OF BILINGUAL TERMINOLOGICAL DICTIONARY IN THE FIELD OF LAW

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Abstract. *Fostering high citizenship of the individual, respect for the laws, intransigence towards any violations of the law, readiness to actively participate in the protection of law and order - this is the task of legal education. Undoubtedly, popular legal literature occupies a special place in legal education and upbringing of the population.*

Keywords: *legal term, terminological dictionaries, dictionary of legal terms and expressions, legal linguistics.*

Introduction: Currently, the creation of terminological dictionaries in various fields of science that meets the requirements of today is an urgent task of our time. The modern stage of life of the world community is characterized by active intercultural interaction, exchange of professional information, in the process of which the use of terminology plays a significant role.

Terminological vocabulary is contrasted with commonly used vocabulary, firstly, “by its meaningful connection and objects of a certain special area, and secondly, by the fact that within the framework of special communication it has a very high frequency, from the point of view of the vocabulary as a whole, it is only to a very small extent included in the sphere of sufficiently frequent vocabulary” [1, pp. 171-172].

In the works of V.P.Danilenko terminology is qualified as “belonging to the language of science, as the main, most significant and informative part of the lexical system of the language of science” [2, p. 15].

G.O.Vinokur, exploring individual issues of word formation of scientific terms, made an interesting remark: “Terms are not special words, but only words in a special function. A special function in which a word acts as a term is the function of a name. A household term is the name of a thing. Meanwhile, a scientific-theoretical term is certainly the name of a concept” [38, pp. 3-55].

The definition of the concept of “legal term” is given in the “Big Legal Dictionary” from I. Sukhareva, D.V. Zorkina [3].

Law terms – an element of legal *technology*, verbal designations of state legal concepts, with the help of which the content of legal regulations of the state is expressed and consolidated. Legal terms can be classified into three types: a) generally significant terms (characterized by the fact that they are used in the usual sense and are understandable to everyone); b) special legal terms have special legal content, for example: *necessary party, limitation period*, etc.; c) special technical terms reflect the area of special knowledge - *technology, economics, medicine, etc., for example: substandard products, safety regulations, etc.*

The use of legal terms must meet the following requirements: 1) the same term in a particular legal act must be used unambiguously; 2) terms must be generally recognized, i.e. used

in everyday life, and not invented by the developers of legal regulations; 3) terms cannot but have a stable character, i.e. must retain their special meaning in each new legal act [3, p.782].

The features of legal terminology were first considered by the professor of jurisprudence, first at Kharkov, and then Novorossiysk / Odessa / universities V.D. Katkov. So, based on the ideas of A.A. Potebni /his teaching on the immediate and further meaning of words/, V.D. Katkov wrote two large books in which this problem was considered: “Jurisprudentiae novum organon” (Logic and jurisprudence reformed by general linguistics) volume I Civilistics, Odessa, 1913 and “Towards the analysis of the basic concepts of jurisprudence”, Kharkov, 1903. However, it should be noted that in general these works of V.D.Katkov are not strictly linguistic studies [4, p.10].

Problems associated with the linguistic understanding of relevant concepts took an important place in linguistics only in the 20th century. [4, p.9].

Legal terminology has many similarities with any other terminology. Legal terms, like any terms, strive for unambiguity, for stylistic neutrality within their scope of application, and are included in certain terminological series.

At the same time, even in this area, specific features characteristic of legal terms should be noted.

In a protocol, an official letter, a report, a statement and in many other types of business texts, the following phrases are common: due to absence (and not “because there is not”), there is and is not available (instead of “is” and “no”), take measures in relation to the seizure of valuables; compensation for damage caused due to defects in goods or services; separation of a legal entity; legal capacity of a legal entity; life imprisonment; privacy. As we can see, a business document is full of verbal nouns. This is one of the main specific properties of the term.

The creation of bilingual terminological dictionaries will help to navigate a large volume of professional terminology.

Terminological dictionaries are dictionaries containing the terminology of one or more special fields of knowledge or activity [5].

Compiling a bilingual terminological dictionary requires solving such problems as the need to determine the criteria for including a term in a terminological dictionary, principles for designing a terminological dictionary, and organizing the presentation of terminological units in the dictionary. In the course of the historical development of the Russian and Uzbek languages, very significant differences have developed in them, in particular in their vocabulary, regarding both the level of expression and the level of content.

The commonality of thinking and the commonality of the world determine the possibility of a certain equivalence of texts in different languages. However, the equivalence of texts does not mean the equivalence of their constituent elements, in particular words [6, p.26].

National legal language and legal terms play an important role in ensuring the rule of law and further reform of the judicial system, high-quality development of draft resolutions, increasing legal education and culture of citizens.

Therefore, over the years of independence, lawyers and linguists have created many annotated and translated dictionaries in the field of law (1993, 1999, 2002, 2003, 2009, 2011, 2014, 2020), the Legal Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan was published, the Ministry of Justice launched the National Legal Internet Portal of the Republic of Uzbekistan (huquqiportal.uz).

However, in practice today problems arise in the field of regulation (unification and standardization) of our legal terms.

In particular, one legal concept is presented in different forms in regulatory and other legal documents. To support this, let us give several examples: the Russian terminological combination “executive power” in various sources in the Uzbek language is given as ijro hokimiyati, ijro etish hokimiyati, ijro etuvchi hokimiyat; показание - ko‘rsatuv, ko‘rsatma, ko‘rgazma, ko‘rgazuv, guvohlik, so‘roq berish; intentionally - bilib turib, bila turib, bilgan holda, qasddan; criminal case - jinoyat ishi, jinoiy ish; statement of claim - da'vo arizasi, da'vo ariza, da'vo-ariza; administrative coercion - fuqarolik majburlov, fuqarolik majburlash, fuqarolik majbur etish; Personal inspection - shaxsiy ko‘rikdan o‘tkazish, shaxsni ko‘rikdan o‘tkazish и др.

The use of legal terms in such a variety of forms leads to negative situations in legal practice, since such legal terms have semantically specific semantic subtleties, and when they are given in a legal text, these subtleties of the meaning of the word appear even more strongly, expressing different meanings. This leads to different understandings and interpretations by both specialists and non-specialists and in practice has a negative impact on the process of their implementation.

In legal terms this is absolutely unacceptable. Because legal documents must be clear and precise. The reader must understand one and only one meaning that the lawyer intends. If the law is not clear to everyone, then it will not ensure law and order in the country, but will create chaos. In addition, the distortion of some of our legal terms has a negative impact on the development of legal consciousness and legal culture of our citizens.

In this regard, one of the most important tasks facing our lawyers and linguists today is the regulation (unification and standardization) of the system of legal terms and, on this basis, the development of a unified electronic legal thesaurus platform for the entire judicial system of our country. The scientific regulation of terms in each field is a continuous process. Strict adherence to terminological principles and norms should be the main criterion.

Based on demand and needs, we (in collaboration with Sh.N.Kuchimov) created the “Russian-Uzbek Dictionary of Legal Terms and Expressions.” When creating the dictionary, the authors relied on deep scientific principles of jurisprudence and the Russian and Uzbek literary and legal languages, giving special alternatives to each legal term, with a special emphasis on the unification and standardization of legal terms.

The dictionary contains about nine thousand legal terms, covering almost all areas of law: the theory of state and law; constitutional law; criminal law; criminal proceedings; administrative law; civil law, family law, labor law, international law, etc.

In addition, when compiling this dictionary, the authors tried to create a dictionary based on the requirements and rules of the science “Legal Linguistics”, which is rapidly developing today in developed countries, that is, assessing the content and essence of each legal concept, they approached it from the point of view of both legal, and linguistic sciences, continuing the traditions of the history of Russian and Uzbek legal lexicography.

V.V.Dubchinsky includes the following criteria for including a term in the terminological dictionary: 1) frequency of use of this term in texts on the specialty; 2) its value for a given terminology system; 3) the relevance of the term in certain contexts of a given sublanguage [5].

When compiling the “Russian-Uzbek Dictionary of Legal Terms and Expressions.” we were guided by such principles as

- *the principle of consistency*. Systematicity presupposes the thematic coherence of all selected lexical units;

- *the principle of communicative value*, which plays an important role in the selection of vocabulary for the terminological dictionary. In the process of implementing this principle, when selecting lexical units for inclusion in the dictionary, priority is given to lexical units that have the widest combinatory capabilities;

- *the principle of complexity*, which is to consolidate in dictionary form the results of studying all levels of the language structure;

- *the principle of educational orientation*.

One of the main aspects of developing a bilingual terminological dictionary is solving the problem associated with the development of the structure of the dictionary (the structure of a dictionary entry, the type of dictionary definitions, the relationship between different types of information about a word, etc.

The leading terms in the dictionary we have developed are arranged in alphabetical order, and terms consisting of words that are written with a hyphen should be considered in the alphabet as words written together.

Each dictionary entry is provided with a translation into Uzbek, synonyms, and, if necessary, a definition.

The main and difficult stage of working on the dictionary was the process of selecting an equivalent, a definition in the Uzbek language, containing basic information about the lexical unit. The first element of the definition is the actual translation of the main word or combination. Since the dictionary reflects the actual state of two languages, we indicate the established equivalent as a translation. If there are two or more established translation options, they are listed in order of decreasing prevalence. For example, *liquidate* - tugatmoq, yo'qotmoq, barham bermoq, bitirmoq; *accusation*, c. - ayblash, qoralash, gunohkor qilish.

In some cases, to define a Russian term, a semantic characteristic is indicated in the form of a descriptive translation that accurately conveys the meaning of the unit being translated. For example, *codification*. - kodifikatsiya qilish, kodeks tuzish, qonunlar majmuini tuzish.

For compound terms, an alphabetical nested system has been adopted. According to this system, terms consisting of defined words and definitions should be searched for by defined (leading) words.

For example, the term civil law should be searched in the nest law.

If the leading word of a vocabulary nest is repeated in the phrases given in this article, then a tilde sign (~) is placed in its place.

The dictionary uses the following system of delimiters: similar values are separated by a comma; different values are separated by numbers.

The dictionary used only the most common abbreviations of words within articles, traditional for dictionaries and reference books. For example, m. is masculine, g. – feminine, p. – neuter, plural - plural.

In compiling this dictionary, almost all specialized legal dictionaries, encyclopedias, legal and linguistic scientific sources published in our country were used.

The functions of dictionaries are their tasks in general. The purpose of dictionaries is their focus on serving specific types of activities. According to the scientist V.V.Dubichinsky [5, P. 98], “a lexicographical complex description designed for everyone will not be needed by anyone.”

Today, the Republic of Uzbekistan has entered a new renaissance period of its development, Uzbek statehood is being rebuilt on the basis of its many years of experience, and extensive reforms are being carried out towards building a fair civil society in the socio-political,

legal, economic and spiritual spheres. This has a positive effect on people's mood, increasing the spiritual and legal potential of every citizen.

In this regard, improving state and social construction, ensuring the rule of law and further reforming the judicial system, set out in the Action Strategy for the five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021 and other regulatory documents, the national legal language and legal terms play an important role in the quality development projects, improving legal education and culture of citizens.

We really hope that the "Russian-Uzbek Dictionary of Legal Terms and Expressions" that we have developed will provide direct practical assistance to deputies of the Oliy Majlis and members of the Senate in the complex process of drafting bills; will contribute to the development of accurate, clear and high-quality documents for all law enforcement officials in the country (justice, law enforcement agencies, state security services, prosecutors, judiciary, etc.) in accordance with the requirements of legal technology; will play an important role in the scientific and educational activities of professors and students of law schools; will serve as an important source of high legal literacy and legal culture of all our citizens, their correct and appropriate use of legal terms.

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